

Pakistani Electronic Media and its Contribution in Engendering Social Exclusion for the Persons with Disabilities

Asmaa Azeem, Shahnila Tariq, Syeda Zahra Jafri, Zikra Faiz, Gulfam Nawaz

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 22, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Exclusion, Inclusion, Disabilities, Electronic Media, Persons With Special Needs</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5719741</p>	<p><i>The current study's target was to inspect the role of Pakistani electronic media in generating social awareness towards the inclusion of communities with disabilities. The core objective of the study was to investigate the contribution of electronic media in creating social exclusion for persons with disabilities in society as the exclusionary practices can be seen in our community. The sample were taken from different TV channels, professionals with special needs from various organizations of Lahore city. It was a descriptive study by nature and the source of data collection was a questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed by the researchers, which reached an acceptable level of reliability. The data was personally collected and analyzed through SPSS. The sample consisted of 24 media employees, 25 students with special needs and 23 employees. Reliability statistics showed that the instrument was reliable at 0.88. One sample t-test was applied to see the significant difference among respondents' opinions and following variables age, education, marital status and gender.</i></p>

Introduction

In our daily life, we need to communicate and socialize. Communication is the key to connecting with and building social networks at a broader range, whether verbal or nonverbal.

Same as mass media which is also a more powerful means of communication. Media have control over our lives, thinking direction and influence our life.

It has been proved that media creates an incredible difference in our lives. Media plays a vital role in warning about upcoming crises. It also vigilantly warns the community when there are some red alarms in our surroundings. Through electronic media, the community becomes updated and well informed. The media decides which stories are significant for coverage in newspapers, magazines, and Television. Mass media connects us with various people even though we have no direct interaction with these groups. It is indeed a solid agent to socialize. Media is one of the effective sources to learn many behaviours and values. Media also helps us in learning norms (Michael .G. & Teri k .W. 1989). Facing the issue of literacy ratio and less enrollment in schools, however, the Government of Pakistan is also resilient to spread awareness for the rights of every citizen without discrimination. The president of Pakistan (Govt. of Pakistan 2020) shared that media has a crucial role in scattering awareness for the constitutional rights of individuals with disabilities in Pakistan. In the same statement, the Govt. of Pakistan has also contracted with China to project and provide assistive technology for persons with disabilities. Dichotomous to this the electronic media has its agenda points to portray the facets of disability, drive the general community and necessities for the "kind of rights" of persons who have any type of disability. The State has also shown its responsibility by announcing that these persons should be called "differently able" instead of disabling. The media must focus on the strengths and potentials rather than the disabling conditions.

Electronic media has the capacity for bringing change in our behaviours that directly affect our immediate ecology. The power of mass media can shape up any society. When people started to oppose, it is an indicator of a power failure because people started thinking in a diversified manner and representing their point of view in their own logical and critical thinking direction. The first stage is to make the public understandable to recognize society by criticizing it positively. It can better protect the core of interest of societal people.

Sam Phillips (2018) shared statistics about the discernments of people in the United Kingdom that, however, the state of the UK is catering for the needs of 13.3million community persons with disabilities. Only 24% of residents without disabilities are not very comfortable talking about it. In contrast, the rest of the members are reluctant to discuss such members of society. During the arrangements for the occasion of RIO Para-Olympics 2016, Channel 4 took the initiative and invested its one million £ for broadcasting of advertisements in highlighting the multiple endowments and features of the community individuals who were with some disabilities. This investment was announced yearly, and the award money focused on the diverse domain of diversity to encourage the advertising agencies to embrace inclusive, innovative crusades.

In this regard, the media's role is crucial for creating awareness, advocating and endorsing the constitutional rights of persons with disabilities. For instance, image descriptions and stories highlighted on the different media sources can intensely impact public opinion and help establish social norms anywhere in the world. Communities with disabilities are rarely positively highlighted by the media. The manner through which mass media feature persons with disabilities has often been very biased. The primary focus of our electronic media is to reflect the misery and forward social sympathies rather than showing empathy towards the underprivileged community of the disabled.

Consequently, we see what media wants to show us “a depressingly stereotyped person with a particular disability. Instead of onscreen their abilities and potentials, their disabling characters are focused. It is widespread to recognize such communities as reasons of lousy luck, donations or health intervention that have to overawe disastrous and incapacitating conditions.

Mass media can be a decisive gadget in engendering awareness, refuting stigmatization and distorted information. It can be a dynamic power to transform social apprehensions and represent persons with disabilities like human diversity. This can be possible if mass media focuses on increasing the consciousness and acceptance of the issues related to disability and the diversified needs of all. Electronic media can vigorously remove barriers, leading to effective and successful inclusion of differently-abled persons in all facets of communal life. Undeniably, the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities entails States to create awareness and encounter stereotypes associated with persons with disabilities, together with the encouragement of media to represent individuals with diversified needs in a consistent way with deference for human rights.

Hazlin (2017) also supported and strongly agreed upon that all kinds of media strongly influence its community's thought process and thinking directly. In this study, the researcher portrayed the situation of Malaysia and stated that it is effortless for the media sources to seed what they desire. The researcher shared the cultivation theory as a reference to support his views, presented by Hawkins and Pingree in 1980. Media is mainly driven through its state governing body, for the national interests and the policies, to influence the general public. Furthermore, a lack of understanding of policies and legal allegations related to the provision and availing the rights of persons with disabilities suffer a lot. The perceptions associated with the negative attitudes for the community with diverse needs due to disability depend upon the reflection of disability as a social and economic burden and source of sympathy that create social isolation for the sufferers and their families.

National Commission for persons with *disabilities Act (2018)* also stressed the role of electronic media in the widespread awareness for disabilities and the potentials of persons with different disabilities in diverse contexts.

As Faria, Rubab and Asmaa (2013) reported the research of Jennifer. M. Bowles, Alan. Hayes. (2003) that in every society, any individual who has been considered different from the majority due to any condition is being victimized as a stigma. Stigmatization is just like a practice of labelling towards any individual with their negative identification symbol based on any deformity or loss. As far as disabilities are concerned, many people develop negative attitudes toward the suffering community and realize that it is due to their faulty personalities that don't possess desirable criteria for adjustment. Stronger reflections of stigmatizations force the labelled persons to social exclusion.

Byrne, David, (1999) supported his point of view for the exclusion at a social level by stating that social exclusion is considered the collective phrase for the various multifaceted kinds of social problems that derive from the significant escalation in social disparity. In earlier times, people with disabilities were seen as pulled out communities from society. It was the common practice of any society to exclude the labelled or disable persons from society. In Western culture, sensory impairment is acceptable than neurological impairment. The acceptance depends on age and behavior. Stigmatization is a resource to evaluate the context of any society. Stigmatization reflects the views of society towards disabilities.

As Roberta (2004) stressed, socialization is a mutually shared process that can be considered a reciprocal and dynamic two-way process. Socialization is not a product; it's a lifetime practice involving all human beings via equitable circumstances.

The United Nations (2002) is dedicated to providing equal human rights to all persons, including diverse needs. There is a long historical journey of endorsing these rights worldwide on an equal basis with others to attain an inclusive society for all. The work of the United Nations for persons with disabilities is now reinforced by a legal document, “Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities”. This document further supports and empower persons with disabilities towards better lives and endorse their inclusion in public on an equal basis.

Social inclusion of persons with disabilities is indeed a significant challenge in the recent era. Changing perceptions can make it possible and desirably transform the attitudes of the community.

The attention should be on portraying the positive image of disability on the electronic media supported with an understanding of precise and balanced depiction of disability as a part of everyday life. The media can play a

significant role in highlighting the issues and barriers related to different disabilities to dismiss negative stereotypes and promote their rights and understanding of self-respect.

Moreover, there should be multiple options for representing the abilities of persons with different disabilities on all different kinds of media. There should also be needed to project the need and importance of the support provided by the United Nations for building a nonviolent and inclusive society for all.

The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities can work as a tool to enhance the work of the media in promoting the rights of persons with disabilities, as well as in promoting their access to quality and equity of different resources as; education, employment, health and other areas of development on an equal basis.

As stated by McCallum, Ron (2011), Article 29 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities ('CRPD') supported that endorsing states must guarantee political rights to persons with disabilities and the prospect to enjoy them on an equivalent basis with other citizens. Undoubtedly, the range of disabilities is broad and must be addressed on an equal and equity basis worldwide.

The United Nation's World Development Report (2000) investigated many factors that highly contribute to social exclusion. A few of those are lack of access to social setting, unemployment of persons with disabilities, restricted access to community services, stigmatization of persons with disabilities, inadequate professional training, lack of specified services, bad education services, and the compensation of the extra cost of disability there are deficient economic policies.

Through different awareness campaigns on electronic media like public events, advertisements on prevention and intervention of disabilities, highlighting their constructive roles and other national and international commemoratives can provide outstanding prospects to raise awareness. Programs for disability awareness and associated crucial training can also be a part of professional growth and public awareness. Some annually sponsored opportunities and many campaigns by United Nations include: World Down Syndrome Day celebrates on 21st March, World Autism Awareness Day celebrates on 2nd April, International Day of Persons with Disabilities on 3rd December each year, Human Rights Day on 10th December and Inclusion Saves Lives: DiDRR campaign.

In Pakistan, mostly the electronic media plays a constructive role in bringing social change to any issue. Today news channels and even some newspapers represent some social issues, which help to understand the realities. Pakistani media has focused on social problems in almost every era. In every generation, we can't deny that the issues were always raised to provide justice to the people. Pakistani media has expanded its role in bringing change during the last decade and many causes and matters were brought under one umbrella. It shows us that we are bounded in the barriers of loads of problems and issues even today. Now, the time has arrived when we need to rethink our attitudes towards society (Faria. E. Rubab. Z. & Asmaa. A. 2013).

In Pakistan, media has liberty and independence for creating sensitization towards every social issue. In the case of electronic media, there are various channels and information segments, including news & current affairs, sports, and entertainment. It is now the responsibility of the state to instruct media agencies for projecting and highlighting such issues.

During the year 2014 British Council of Pakistan established a convention research report entitled "Moving from the margins; mainstreaming persons with disabilities in Pakistan". The prime objective of this report was to ripen a better level of understanding towards routine life experiences and needs analysis of the persons with different kinds of disabilities in Pakistan. After compiling the final survey report, they also suggested mainstreaming such persons with special needs. This report also found that Pakistan has almost 27 million persons with different kinds of high and low incidence disabilities. The report also stated that the Pakistani community with disabilities was suffering from a lack of engagement and implementation of inclusive practices. That might be costing from 4.9% to 6.3% of per annum GDP. After concluding a total of sixty (60) interviews from the field experts, they also reported a dire need to restructure and transform stereotypical negative attitudes of society. Moreover, the state should execute legislative measures to protect the rights of persons with all disabilities; purposely, national policies and strategies should be aligned with international practices and criteria, provision of quality educational facilities and employment policy measures and the process should be flexible for creating employment opportunities as per their population ratio.

Islamabad's particular talented exchange program (STEP) is a cross-disability and skill development organization. It is a profit organization promoting disability in Pakistan established in 1997 by persons with disabilities by themselves. It has jointly collaborated with SAMAA TV, one of Pakistan's leading Urdu news channels today. In 2009 they collaboratively started to organize the first ever media workshop on disability at the COMSET Institute on Islamabad to inform and sensitize Pakistani society towards the rights of these persons. STEP has also introduced a dedicated job portal for the disabled with the collaboration of Telenor Pakistan.

Thus, the research-based literature highlighted that the role of mass media, especially electronic media, is crucial in objectifying any social issue that is stigmatized with our stereotypical attitudes. Moreover, during a pandemic, its after-effects and homebound conditions, the children and adults with any kind of disability

become more at risk than before. Consequently, during needs, redundancy, educational emergency, poverty due to such pandemics, and critical health issues, electronic media should adapt accordingly and become more vigilant for spreading awareness so that no individual is mislaid among the general population. At this age of rapidly growing technologically advanced scenario, the rights and responsibilities of citizenship of each member of society cannot be denied. Unless and until rectifying the role of electronic media, we can't meet the global pace to excel. Every citizen should be considered a potentially productive server, and the state must take advantage of it by equitable role distributions among such excluded minorities. In Pakistan, we can observe a pronounced ignorant behavior of media sources, leading towards engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities. If we want to promote inclusive education and the rights of persons with disabilities, we need full support of electronic media.

Objectives of the study

By keeping in view national and international researches, the researchers established few objectives to direct the track of the current study;

1. Comparing the gender-based opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities.
2. Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on their age groups
3. Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on education
4. Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities based on their marital status.

Research questions

1. Was there any significant difference among the respondents' opinions towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities?
2. Was there any significant difference among the respondents' opinions towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities based on their age groups?
3. Was there any significant difference among the respondents' opinions towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities based on education?
4. Was there any significant difference among the respondents' opinions towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities based on their marital status?

Methodology

Research design

The type of research was descriptive by nature, followed by a quantitative approach. It was conducted through survey method with the help of a questionnaire, face to face through personal visits and online mode through google forms.

Research population and Sample

The study population were media persons, students with special needs from different institutions, and professionals.

The sample was conveniently selected. The study sample consisted of the following news channels, GEO, PTV, SUCH and A.PLUS. Twenty four (24) media employees belonged to these news channels. Twenty five (25) students with special needs were conveniently selected from different institutions of Lahore city; University of Management and Technology, University of Punjab, University of Central Punjab and University of Education. At the same time, the remaining data were collected from twenty-three (23) employees with special needs working in the same news channels.

Instrument

For the data collection, a questionnaire was formulated based on research-based literature and a theoretical framework.

All the statements were established and classified under the significant indicators of the questionnaire; community perception, forms of social exclusion, factors of socialization, media campaigns, effects of different academic status and gender, and the provision of rights of the persons with disabilities (Fig.1.1). The question statements were measured against the five-point Likert Scale, strongly agreed, agreed, neutral, disagreed and strongly disagreed. There were thirty-six (36) statements. All statements were self-constructed in a bilingual manner; native language (Urdu) and English language.

Validity was ensured by taking expert opinions of two faculty members from the department of media and communication, two from the department of special needs education and two faculty members from the sociology department. All faculty members were from the University of management and technology, Lahore.

To check the reliability of the research tool, Cronbach alpha Test (Reliability Analysis) was used. Cronbach alpha value of the tool was 0.88, which reflected a higher level of trustworthiness.

Data was collected through a survey type of descriptive research. It was conducted to see the significance of the relationship of the following demographics (age groups, education, marital status and gender) in relation with the role of electronic media and social exclusion; a. Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on gender, b. Comparison of views of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities based on age, c. Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities based on education, d. Comparison of views of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities based on their marital status. To accomplish the objectives mentioned earlier, the researchers conveniently select the sample from different medial channels and universities from the vicinity of Lahore. During the lockdown scenario, because of COVID-19, it was challenging to approach the targeted population. As the academic activities were shifted to online status and in offices, employee strength was minimized. Furthermore, due to public transport restrictions, on-duty employees felt difficulty reaching their workplaces; notably, that situation restricted employees' mobility with different disabilities.

To cater to all the barriers and manage the data collection process, the tool was also shared in soft form; google forms.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics. T-test and ANOVA were performed for analysis to see the significant difference among the opinions of the sample.

Results

Age of the Respondents Table (1) the demographic of age group shows that 47.3% of the respondents were below 30yrs of age, and the rest were 30yrs above.

Gender of the respondent's Table (2) reflected that 86% were male and 14% were females. Whereas 39% were married and 61% were unmarried, as mentioned in Table (3).

The results of Table (4) Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on gender reflects that their views were not significantly different towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on gender.

Findings of Table (5), comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the role of media in creating social exclusion of people with disabilities based on marital status, reflects no significant difference in the views of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on their marital status.

Findings of table (6) Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on age groups reflects a significant difference in the opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on their age groups. The young group (less than 30 years) has a significantly better attitude about the role of media.

Table (7) Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on education reflects that there was a significant difference between the opinions of the respondents towards the role of media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on education. The group with less than 16 years (Masters, in any domain; MA) qualification has a significantly better attitude about the role of media.

Table (8) the analysis of variance was run to see the significant difference among the attitudes of three types of respondents. The ANOVA table indicated no significant difference among the opinions of the three groups ($F=1.5$, $Sig= 0.23$).

Table:1 Age of the Respondents

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Below 30yrs	34	47.3	47.3
Above 30yrs	48	52.7	100
Total		72	100
	72	100	

Table:2 Gender of the respondents

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	62	86	86.1
Female	10	14	100.0
Total	72	100.0	

Table:3 Marital status of the respondents

Responses	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Married	28	39	38.9
Unmarried	44	61	100.0
Total	72	100.0	

Table:4 Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on gender

Gender	N	Mean	Df	T	Sig
Male	62	108.48	70	0.20	0.84
Female	10	110.10			

Table:5 Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on marital status

Status	N	Mean	Df	T	Sig
Married	28	102.82	70	1.76	.08
Unmarried	44	112.45			

Table:6 Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on age groups

Age	N	Mean	df	T	Sig
Less than 30 years	34	117.82	70	3.41	0.001
30 years and above	38	100.55			

Table:7 Comparison of opinions of the respondents towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for the persons with disabilities based on education

Age	N	Mean	df	T	Sig
MA and above	42	102.48	70	2.85	0.006
Below MA	38	117.43			

Table:8 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) to see the significant difference among the attitudes of three types of the respondents

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1565.503	2	782.752	1.502	.230
Within Groups	35967.372	69	521.266		
Total	37532.875	71			

Conclusion & Discussion

Following conclusions based discussion was based on significant findings. The current study results and the reported facts by Sam Phillips (2018) were almost similar. He identified the uncertainty, reluctance and gaps in bridging the social liaison between the communities with disabilities and the general population in the United Kingdom before the year 2016. Similarly, in this research, the researchers investigated the breaches of social inclusion and reached surprising facts at a large scale. After data analysis, it was discovered that there was no significant difference among the respondents' opinions towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social exclusion for persons with disabilities based on gender, marital status.

Whereas there found a significant difference in the respondents' opinions towards the contribution of Pakistani electronic media in engendering social inclusion for the persons with disabilities based on their age groups. The young group (less than 30 years) had a significantly better attitude about the role of media. There was also a significant difference between the respondents' opinions towards the role of media in engendering social inclusion for persons with disabilities based on education. The group with less than 16 years (MA) qualification had a significantly better attitude about the role of media.

Most of the respondents responded that media plays an essential role in our life. Even media builds our public opinion. Electronic media can control human thinking. Most of the respondents replied that media is a source of awareness. Media plays an essential role in health awareness and on different social issues like education. Most of the respondents stated that, unfortunately, electronic media is not creating awareness about disabilities. Electronic media is not giving enough coverage to disabilities. Electronic media shows childish behavior towards disabilities.

Electronic media pays no attention nor strives to produce positive programs regularly for the social inclusion of persons with disabilities. There is a lack of focus on the projection of policies, facilities, good practices, academic access, medical access and the importance of early detection and intervention.

Future implications

The study is beneficial for evaluating electronic media based on its fair equal use and services for all policies based on significant findings. It would also help determine the proper role of electronic media in developing patterns and optimistic attitudes of society towards the rights of persons with disabilities. Media can play an influential role in reducing the negative moods of society towards disability. The media should give respectable positions to the characters who demonstrate disabling feelings. Media policies should be revised by considering different resolutions for social inclusion. Stake holders should professionally collaborate with the media for improving its policy of the “voice of everyone for human and civil rights”.

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Author Information

Dr. Asmaa Azeem

Assistant Professor, Department of Special Needs Education, University of Management and Technology. Lahore, Pakistan

Syeda Zahra Jafri

MS Applied Psychology, Department of applied Psychology

Gulfam Nawaz

Lecturer in Special Education, Division of Education, Township Campus, Lahore

Dr. Shahnila Tariq

Associate professor, Department of Applied Psychology, University of management and technology

Zikra Faiz

Applied Behaviour Analysis Therapist, University of Management & Technology, Lahore Pakistan
